

1 ***Lepidoptera* Abundance and Diversity as a Quantitative Measure of Ecosystem Function**
2 **in Bioretention Design**

3 **R. D. Myers¹, B. Wadzuk², and S. K. Chapman³**

4 ¹ Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Villanova University, 800 E. Lancaster
5 Ave., Villanova, PA 19085 USA

6 ² Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Villanova University, 800 E. Lancaster
7 Ave., Villanova, PA 19085 USA

8 ³ Department of Biology, Villanova University, 800 E. Lancaster Ave., Villanova, PA 19085 USA

9 Corresponding author: Raleigh D. Myers (rmyers6@villanova.edu)

10 **Highlights:**

- 11 • We bridge a gap between engineering and ecology in designs that improve terrestrial
12 ecosystem functions alongside water management.
- 13 • Consideration of *Lepidoptera* in bioretention design can help create functional
14 ecological communities in the urban landscape.
- 15 • Data to make use of *Lepidoptera* in design are available due to the popularity of
16 butterflies among professional and citizen scientists.

17 **Abstract**

18 The choices of engineers and other professionals working in urban environments can either
19 mitigate or exacerbate drivers of ecosystem and biodiversity decline. To date, engineers
20 designing bioretention basins for management of surface runoff in urban environments
21 typically have not considered implications of their design and management decisions on
22 terrestrial ecosystem structure and function. However, a foundation of knowledge sufficient to
23 evaluate design decisions in light of ecosystem functions exists in the fields of engineering and
24 ecology, and this knowledge can be connected to improve design outcomes. Specific
25 bioretention system functions considered in this paper are hydrologic regulation, production,
26 nutrient retention, and habitat provisioning. We 1) review existing knowledge on the use of
27 quantitative criteria to advance terrestrial ecosystem objectives in bioretention design, with a
28 focus on *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity as a proxy for these terrestrial ecosystem
29 functions, 2) report results of a structured literature review identifying gaps in knowledge and
30 interdisciplinary communication limiting achievement of terrestrial ecosystem objectives, and
31 3) propose a novel design and plant choice approach to fill these gaps. We close by proposing a
32 series of questions for future research and offering recommendations for applying research
33 outcomes to professional practice.

34 **Plain Language Summary**

35 Wild plants and animals are declining around the world due to human activity. In urban areas,
36 engineers play a key role in managing water-related challenges such as flooding and water
37 pollution, but typical engineering design practice does not consider the functioning of the land-
38 based ecosystem. Engineers and ecologists can share information and work together in urban
39 areas to improve the design of rain gardens and bioretention basins. These basins can manage
40 urban runoff while improving habitat for moths and butterflies and enhancing the function of
41 the urban ecosystem.

42 **1 Introduction**

43 **1.1 Problem Statement**

44 Engineers designing bioretention basins for management of surface runoff in urban
45 environments typically do not consider implications of their design, plant choices, and
46 management decisions on terrestrial ecosystem structure and function (e.g., Cook et al., 2023;
47 Prudencio and Null, 2018). A foundation of knowledge to evaluate design decisions in light of
48 ecosystem function exists in the fields of engineering and ecology, but historically there has
49 been a gap in knowledge sharing and collaboration between these disciplines. There is a need
50 to bridge this gap as engineers seek to advance bioretention designs that meet an increasingly
51 wide range of objectives while never losing site of core water quantity and water quality
52 management objectives.

53

54

55

56 1.2 Notes on Terminology

57 To begin bridging the gap between the disciplines of engineering and ecology, we will
58 employ a definition of the term “ecosystem function” that is recognizable to both disciplines
59 and intended for application within the narrow domain of bioretention design. We herein
60 define “function” as work performed by a designed system (herein, a bioretention basin
61 receiving urban surface runoff), where the work has been identified as desirable in the
62 judgment of the system’s design team. This definition is logically consistent with definitions of
63 the term “ecosystem service” commonly employed by ecologists (Costanza, 1997; Jax, 2005),
64 and it is also appropriate to serve as a basis for engineering design. In ecology, value judgments
65 or comparison to a suitable reference state may be employed to determine what work will be
66 considered desirable from a human perspective (e.g., Jax, 2005). When a system is designed by
67 engineers, desired functions of the system typically are determined by a project owner or
68 stakeholders and stated explicitly at commencement of the planning and design process (e.g.,
69 Yoe and Orth, 1996). Engineers then apply scientific principles to choose the components and
70 structure of a system (including soil characteristics and plants, where relevant) expected to
71 achieve the desired functions while considering external conditions acting on the defined
72 boundaries of the system (Beyers and Odum, 1993). There is an opportunity to either expand
73 the design team beyond engineers or to equip engineers with understandable and usable
74 metrics to design more inclusively.

75 In the context of this paper, specific bioretention system functions to be considered will
76 be (1) hydrologic regulation, (2) production, or facilitation of energy and carbon flows between
77 trophic levels (i.e., “up the food chain”), (3) nutrient retention, and (4) habitat provision.
78 Pollination and nectar provision will be mentioned, but a detailed treatment of these functions
79 will be considered outside the scope of this paper. The term “biodiversity” will be considered a
80 description of the characteristics or ordered biological components of the system (Chao et al.,
81 2014; Pavoine and Bonsall, 2011), analogous to engineering system characteristics such as soil
82 properties or hydraulic structure configuration. We will not attempt to value functions
83 performed in financial units.

84 1.3 Overview and Organization

85 In this review, we 1) review existing knowledge on the use of quantitative criteria to
86 advance terrestrial ecosystem objectives in bioretention design, with a focus on *Lepidoptera*
87 abundance and diversity as a proxy for key terrestrial ecosystem functions, 2) demonstrate
88 through results of a structured literature review that a knowledge gap exists (*Lepidoptera* and
89 bioretention basins have never been studied together), and 3) propose a novel design approach
90 to fill this gap. We argue that to successfully engineer bioretention systems to advance
91 ecological objectives, design criteria must be employed that meet two key requirements. The
92 criteria must directly measure or serve as effective proxy measures for terrestrial ecosystem
93 functions. There also must be an ability to predict performance of the bioretention system in
94 advance, in terms of the chosen criteria, as a consequence of specific bioretention design
95 decisions. With this knowledge, engineers and other professionals involved in bioretention
96 design will be able to make choices that improve biodiversity and ecosystem functions such as
97 facilitation of carbon, nutrient and energy flows between trophic levels with minimal tradeoffs

98 in meeting other performance objectives and regulatory requirements expected of urban
99 stormwater management systems.

100 To provide context for introduction of ecological design criteria, Section 2 briefly
101 summarizes the historical background and policy framework for urban stormwater
102 management design in the United States. The focus is on bioretention, an umbrella term for a
103 range of commonly employed nature-based solutions incorporating soil, water, and plants at
104 ground level. We describe the expanding number of performance objectives that stormwater
105 management planners and designers are asked to consider in parallel. These expanding
106 objectives now include terrestrial ecosystem functional objectives such as providing habitat and
107 nutrition for a diverse range of plant and animal life and facilitating the flow of nutrients and
108 energy between trophic levels in the ecosystem. In Section 3, we briefly summarize literature
109 on the “sixth extinction” and the “insect apocalypse”, making a case that the decisions of
110 planners and engineers working in urban environments can either contribute to these negative
111 trends or potentially contribute to their mitigation.

112 In Section 4, we explain why bioretention basins are typically nutrient-enriched
113 ecosystems and why this enrichment may place limits on biodiversity that can be achieved in
114 these systems. In Section 5, we make a case that an important terrestrial ecosystem objective
115 for practicing stormwater designers is to create or restore functioning food chains incorporating
116 multiple trophic levels in and around bioretention basins. Insect herbivores, and specifically the
117 insect order *Lepidoptera*, including butterflies and moths, are identified as an important
118 “missing link” that can transfer energy and matter from bioretention plants to vertebrates,
119 creating functional ecological communities in the urban landscape (Narango et al., 2020). In
120 Section 6, we demonstrate that data required to make quantitative use of *Lepidoptera* in
121 bioretention design are extensive and widely available due to the popularity of butterflies
122 among both professional and citizen scientists. In Section 7, we present results of a structured
123 literature search and a summary of other recent review and synthesis articles to demonstrate
124 that the quantitative use of *Lepidoptera* in this context has never before been reported in
125 published literature. Finally, in Section 8 we propose a research agenda aimed at connecting
126 and exploiting this existing data across disciplines while also developing new knowledge to
127 inform a design decision framework. This new framework will be of use to professional
128 bioretention planners and designers who wish to consider terrestrial ecosystem objectives in
129 practice.

130 **2 A Brief History of Multiple-Objective Urban Stormwater Management Design in the United** 131 **States**

132 Urbanization profoundly alters the hydrologic characteristics of watersheds by
133 converting permeable surfaces (soil, vegetation) to sealed impermeable materials including
134 pavement and buildings. One typology characterizes land use as “suburban” when 10-25% of
135 the land surface is converted to an impervious condition, “urban” when 25-60% of the land
136 surface is converted, and “ultra-urban” when greater than 60% of the land surface is converted
137 (National Academy of Sciences, 2009). Most engineering disciplines have not traditionally
138 focused on biodiversity, but choices made by engineers affect the characteristics of the built

139 environment and therefore the extent and quality of habitat for plants and animals in
140 developed areas (Prudencio and Null, 2018).

141 Prior to approximately the 1970s in the United States, water management efforts in
142 urbanized and urbanizing areas typically focused on mitigating risks to human life and property
143 posed by increased flood peaks (Debo and Reese, 2002). The most acute risks often were
144 managed by construction of combined sewer systems, channelization of urban streams to move
145 peak flows quickly downstream, or construction of large storage structures such as detention
146 ponds. These objectives often could be accomplished with relatively simple structures
147 consisting of concrete, earth, or mown grass along with hydraulic control structures (e.g., Davis
148 et al., 2022).

149 With the advent of the Clean Water Act in the 1970s, governments at all levels began to
150 pay more attention to protection of aquatic ecosystems by limiting pollutant loads to surface
151 waters. Initial efforts focused on point sources such as industrial process discharges and
152 municipal wastewater treatment plants, but gradually efforts expanded to encompass diffuse
153 pollutant sources including urban stormwater (Davis et al., 2022).

154 By the 1990s, some state and local programs included measures to prevent erosive
155 flows from damaging the structure of downstream ecosystems, such as stream banks, channels,
156 and substrates needed by aquatic organisms (e.g., Prince George’s County, 2000). Gradually,
157 many jurisdictions adopted objectives of mimicking a pre-development water balance, taking
158 into account the various fates of surface runoff including groundwater recharge, stream
159 baseflow replenishment, surface runoff, and evapotranspiration (National Academy of Sciences,
160 2009). This multiple-objective design approach has the advantage of addressing several
161 objectives at once: peak flow management, control of pollutant loads to downstream aquatic
162 ecosystems, prevention of physical damage to downstream aquatic ecosystems,
163 and maintaining a flow duration regime that supports a wide variety of aquatic life (e.g., Davis
164 et al., 2022).

165 This broader perspective on the hydrologic cycle and biogeochemical cycles within
166 stormwater management facilities required stormwater engineers to learn more about the
167 dynamics of soil-water-plant systems and to apply this understanding to inform design choices.
168 For example, research is available on soil mixes able to provide sufficient infiltration rates and
169 pollutant removal rates to achieve desired hydrologic cycle manipulation and pollutant removal
170 in bioretention basins (e.g., Bratieres et al., 2008; Hsieh et al., 2007; Lucas and Greenway,
171 2011). Qualitative advice on soil composition and plants appropriate for
172 stormwater management facilities is tabulated in guidance for public infrastructure design and
173 private building/zoning code requirements at the state and municipal level (e.g., Center for
174 Watershed Protection and Maryland Department of the Environment, 2009; Philadelphia Water
175 Department, 2020; Shaw and Schmidt, 2003). More recently, quantitative research is beginning
176 to shed light on specific plant species and plant characteristics that enhance pollutant removal
177 in stormwater management systems, thereby helping protect downstream aquatic ecosystems
178 (e.g., Payne et al., 2018). Evidence supports an increase in hydraulic conductivity, permeability,
179 and pollutant removal in systems with plants compared to systems with no plants. This

180 improved performance can be linked to the presence and characteristics of roots (Dagenais et
181 al., 2018).

182 With this increased understanding of plants' role in stormwater design, in addition to
183 the dynamics of water and soil, a natural progression is for engineers and other urban design
184 professionals to consider the impacts of the systems they are designing on terrestrial habitat
185 and biodiversity more broadly, both at the site scale and at the landscape/watershed scale. At
186 the landscape scale, animals and seeds are able to move and disperse from place to place over
187 time and bioretention design can facilitate this movement and ecosystem energy flow.

188 Water resources engineers and other professionals working in the stormwater
189 management area make decisions intended to mitigate the hydrologic effects of urbanization,
190 including decisions about the sizing, configuration, and placement of bioretention basins and
191 the choice of vegetation. Engineers, urban planners, and other professionals also influence land
192 use and urban design decisions made at larger scales, such as design and implementation of
193 building and zoning codes. These large-scale decisions of urban design professionals therefore
194 can have an outside influence on the extent, quality, and connectivity of habitat particularly in
195 and around urban cores. The characteristics of the urban environment also affect the resilience
196 of plant and animal populations impacted by climate change (e.g., Correa Ayram et al., 2016). It
197 has not yet been determined to what extent advancing these terrestrial ecosystem objectives
198 may complement or may require tradeoffs with the more traditional engineering objectives
199 such as controlling the hydrologic cycle and preventing pollutants from reaching downstream
200 aquatic systems.

201 This paper will focus on bioretention systems, and we are using this term to refer to a
202 range of common configuration options for urban nature-based solutions incorporating
203 intermittent surface ponding, soil, plants, and hydraulic outflow controls. Related terms found
204 in the literature include rain gardens, stormwater planters, bioinfiltration, biofiltration,
205 bioswales, and vegetated swales (e.g., see Prudencio and Null, 2018 and Cook et al., 2023 for
206 broader discussions of green stormwater infrastructure terms). Bioretention plants may include
207 herbaceous vegetation, shrubs, or trees depending on urban design context. Engineered
208 structures designed to enclose the roots of urban trees (described by terms including tree pits,
209 tree boxes, and tree trenches) can fit the definition of bioretention employed in this paper
210 provided these facilities incorporate sufficient soil and receive runoff from a surrounding urban
211 drainage area. Wetlands, green roofs, and unvegetated systems are excluded from the
212 definition of bioretention used in this paper.

213 Bioretention sizing and configuration varies with design objectives, climate, and
214 watershed characteristics, but the designs have certain common elements. Bioretention basins
215 typically incorporate a surface depression allowing ponding and fully saturated soils to develop
216 during and for a period of time after wet weather inflows. Ponding typically persists for less
217 than one day to less than one week, leading to dry surface conditions and unsaturated, aerobic
218 soil conditions between the majority of wet weather events (Prince George's County et al.,
219 1994). Depending on site-specific conditions, underlying soil or urban fill materials may require
220 an underdrain structure with a hydraulic control (e.g., an orifice) to achieve drawdown times in
221 the target range (Prince George's County, 2007). The systems typically concentrate runoff from

222 multiple units of urbanized drainage area to a single unit of system surface area (Roy-Poirier et
223 al., 2010).

224 **3 The Sixth Extinction and the Insect Apocalypse**

225 A large body of evidence indicates that wild plants and animals are disappearing around
226 the world. The total number of species is decreasing, rare species are under increased threat of
227 extinction, and the population sizes of many common species are decreasing (e.g., Dirzo et al.
228 2014). Widespread population declines and elevated extinction risks have been documented in
229 vertebrates. For example, Almond et al. (2022) documented a 69% average decline in
230 abundance of monitored bird, mammal, fish, reptile, and amphibian species worldwide
231 between 1970 and 2016. Sekercioglu et al. (2004) projected that 6-14% of all bird species will
232 be extinct by 2100, with 7-25% of all species reaching a point of functional extinction at which
233 populations are not sustainable in the long term.

234 The trends of widespread population declines and elevated extinction risks also are
235 being observed in insects on multiple continents. Forister et al. (2019) stated that “insects are
236 experiencing a multicontinental crisis that is apparent as reductions in abundance, diversity,
237 and biomass”. The magnitude and severity of the trend is such that it has been described as an
238 “insect apocalypse” (Goulson, 2021). Sharp declines in *Lepidoptera* species (butterflies,
239 skippers, and moths) have been documented on multiple continents. In the United Kingdom,
240 Warren et al. (2021) reported 8% of species extinct and a 50% decline in overall abundance
241 since 1976, while in the Netherlands the corresponding figures were 20% of species extinct and
242 a 50% decline in abundance. In Belgium, Warren et al. (2021) reported 29% of species extinct
243 and a 30% decline in abundance between 1992 and 2007. In the U.S. State of Ohio, Wepprich et
244 al. (2019) studied 21 years of data on 81 butterfly species, reporting a cumulative 33%
245 reduction in abundance over this period and three times as many species experiencing declines
246 as increases. Across the United States, the non-profit organization NatureServe has classified
247 16% of butterfly and skipper species and 20% of moth species as being at risk of extinction
248 (NatureServe, 2023). There is a lively scientific debate about data collection methods and
249 potential biases in the literature discussing these insect declines, and a comprehensive survey
250 of this debate is beyond the scope of the current paper aimed at an audience of engineers and
251 other urban design professionals. Nonetheless, there is a widespread view among scientists
252 that declines in numbers of species and in abundance of many common species are occurring
253 and need to be addressed (Wagner et al., 2021b).

254 A range of contributing causes of species declines has been identified. While there is
255 debate about the relative importance of the contributing factors, a loose consensus has
256 emerged that principal drivers of insect decline are land use change including habitat loss (e.g.,
257 Habel et al., 2019), urbanization (Concepcion et al., 2023), climate change (Halsch et al., 2012;
258 Harvey et al., 2023), agricultural practices (Raven and Wagner, 2021) including neonicotinoid
259 insecticides (van Deynze et al., 2024; Janousek et al., 2023), introduced species (Wagner et al.,
260 2021b; Yoon and Read, 2016), and pollution, with excess nitrogen loads being a particularly
261 impactful form of pollution (e.g., Forister et al., 2019; Wagner et al., 2021b). Bioretention can
262 address some of these causes directly, including habitat loss and nitrogen loads in surface

263 runoff, while playing a partial role in mitigating broader urbanization impacts and helping urban
264 areas adapt to climate change.

265 Some of the stressors believed to be driving insect decline are most acute in more rural,
266 agricultural regions of Western Europe and North America, where much of the data collection
267 underlying studies of insect decline has taken place (Habel et al., 2019). These stressors include
268 deforestation to clear land for agriculture, intense pesticide and fertilizer application, and
269 aggregation of smaller farms with more varied land uses into large, highly mechanized farms
270 with little or no suitable habitat for wild plants and animals (Raven and Wagner, 2021).

271 A group of stressors leading to insect decline tends to co-occur in densely populated
272 urban and suburban areas. This group includes conversion of forests and other natural habitats
273 to residential, commercial, and industrial land uses which drastically alter historical hydrology
274 (National Academy of Sciences, 2009), fragment and pollute remaining habitat, and reduce the
275 availability of host plants and nectar sources (e.g., Fenoglio et al. 2021). Exotic species,
276 fertilizers, and pesticides are introduced in urban environments through landscaping practices,
277 while urban heat island effects, sound pollution and light pollution in urban areas also can have
278 impacts on insects and other wildlife (Wagner et al., 2021b). Of particular concern, combustion
279 of fossil fuels in urban areas is a key source of atmospheric nitrogen deposited across rural,
280 urban, and aquatic environments (Vitousek et al., 1997), and excess nitrogen loads have been
281 linked to reduced abundance and diversity of organisms at multiple trophic levels, including
282 plants (Bobbink et al., 2010) and animals (Betzholtz et al., 2013; Nijssen et al., 2017; Poyry et al.,
283 2017).

284 Climate change is impacting insects and is expected to be an increasingly important
285 driver of insect declines in the future (Harvey et al., 2023). Along with increasing average air
286 temperatures, insects will be impacted by changes in the severity and frequency of extreme
287 heat and cold periods, fires, storms, floods and drought conditions (Wagner et al., 2021b).

288 Declines in insect abundance and diversity are concerning in their own right, and
289 because of the key position of insects in the trophic hierarchy, they are an indicator of the
290 decline of ecosystem functions more broadly. In the urban environment, human-driven changes
291 in historical land use, land cover, hydrology, and pollutant loads are drivers of insect declines
292 and ecosystem function declines more generally, although the relative contribution of each of
293 these drivers has not been established. Engineered stormwater management systems are
294 intended to mitigate many of these environmental impacts in urban areas, and therefore their
295 design and locations can be expected to affect insects. However, the impacts of these systems
296 on insects have not been established and this gap in knowledge warrants further investigation.

297 **4 Engineered Ecosystems, Excess Resources, and Biodiversity**

298 One function of a stormwater control such as bioretention is to intercept, concentrate,
299 and retain nitrogen and other nutrients in runoff from the surrounding land area. This nutrient
300 retention function protects downstream aquatic ecosystems by preventing a portion of
301 nutrients in surface runoff from reaching them. A bioretention basin can be thought of as an
302 engineered terrestrial ecosystem that is intentionally nutrient enriched by design, in contrast to
303 a natural ecosystem where undesired nutrient enrichment typically indicates management

304 objectives have not been met. While this nutrient enrichment is intentional, it may require
305 acceptance of tradeoffs between localized diversity of the engineered terrestrial ecosystem
306 (e.g., a bioretention basin and its urbanized watershed) and diversity of downstream aquatic
307 and terrestrial ecosystems the engineered system is intended to protect.

308 When an ecosystem receives an excess of a particular resource such as a nutrient load,
309 it is able to organize itself to make maximum use of that resource by prioritizing development
310 of components able to process that excess. All other things being equal, a system with a regular
311 inflow of excess nutrients, a eutrophic system, will tend to be less diverse because a few
312 species that are best able to process the nutrients will out-compete others. Such a eutrophic
313 ecosystem is able to organize itself to make maximum use of available energy and resources
314 with a relatively simple structure (low diversity, low complexity, and low information content)
315 (Giannetti et al., 2019; Odum, 1988). This state can be a desired outcome in engineered
316 systems because the localized low-diversity, high-productivity system is able to process wastes
317 produced by human activity and thereby allow higher diversity, lower productivity systems to
318 exist downstream (Beyers and Odum, 1993).

319 Bioretention basins receiving urban runoff can be expected to be nutrient-enriched
320 ecosystems when compared to similarly sized soil-water-plant ecosystems not receiving urban
321 runoff. These systems typically receive runoff from an urbanized drainage area that is on the
322 order of 5 to 25 times the area of the bioretention basin surface footprint itself (e.g., Chaves et
323 al., 2024). When mobilized by runoff, nitrogen loads from atmospheric deposition can explain a
324 portion of elevated nutrient concentrations entering the bioretention surface footprint relative
325 to concentrations deposited on an equivalent land area not receiving concentrated runoff (Yang
326 and Toor, 2016). Other sources introduce nutrients to urban runoff including soil erosion,
327 fertilizers, organic material from lawns and gardens, and pet waste (Jani et al., 2020). Sources,
328 loads, and concentrations of pollutants in urban runoff have been extensively studied (e.g.,
329 Burton and Pitt, 2001).

330 Calculations presented in Table 1 demonstrate that nutrient enriched conditions should
331 be expected in bioretention basins receiving urban surface runoff. Using an event mean
332 concentration of 1.95 mg/L total nitrogen reported in the National Stormwater Quality
333 Database (Pitt et al., 2018), if a bioretention facility were to receive approximately 1,000 mm of
334 runoff in a year from a highly impervious drainage area (typical of southeast Pennsylvania) at a
335 ratio of 5-15 units of drainage area per unit of bioretention surface area, the total nitrogen load
336 reaching the facility would be on the order of 100-300 kg N/yr per hectare of bioretention
337 surface area. This load is within the order of magnitude intentionally applied to the land surface
338 in intensive agricultural operations (e.g., Kurze et al., 2018), confirming that bioretention basins
339 receiving urban runoff can be expected to be nutrient-enriched ecosystems relative to similarly
340 sized soil-water-plant ecosystems experiencing minimal human impacts.

341 **Table 1.** Example Nitrogen Loads to the Surface Area of a Bioretention Basin

Drainage Area/Bioretention Surface Area (ratio, including bioretention surface area)	TKN (kg N/ha)	Ammonia (kg N/ha)	Nitrate-Nitrite (kg N/ha)	Total Nitrogen (calculated) (kg N/ha)
5	68.0	16.4	29.3	97
10	135.9	32.8	58.6	195
15	203.9	49.1	88.0	292

342

343 **5 *Lepidoptera* Diversity as a Potential Proxy for Terrestrial Ecosystem Function in Bioretention** 344 **Design**

345 There are several reasons that setting specific quantitative objectives for *Lepidoptera*
346 abundance and diversity makes sense as a bioretention design goal. First, *Lepidoptera* can
347 perform critical functions in the urban ecosystem's bioretention basins such as pollination and
348 energy transfer. Second, *Lepidoptera* have been proposed by a range of authors as reliable
349 indicators of fluctuations and trends in ecosystem functions such as productivity and habitat
350 provisioning. Finally, *Lepidoptera* have been studied extensively and relevant data sets are
351 readily available to researchers and practitioners.

352 5.1 Ecological Functions of *Lepidoptera*

353 *Lepidoptera* perform critical functions within ecosystems. As herbivores in the larval
354 stage, they represent biomass linking primary producers (plants) to higher trophic levels
355 including a majority of all birds, bats, and freshwater fish (Forister et al., 2019; Wagner et al.,
356 2021a). Narango et al. (2020) report that caterpillars transfer more energy from plants to other
357 animals than all other herbivores combined. Illustrating the importance of this transfer,
358 observed declines in insects and insectivorous birds have been closely linked (Tallamy and
359 Shriver, 2021). As pollinators in the adult stage, *Lepidoptera* support the reproduction of
360 flowering plants, and their declines have been linked to declines in overall flower and nectar
361 plant abundance (Wallisdevries et al., 2012). While *Lepidoptera* themselves may be less
362 economically important pollinators of agricultural crops than other insects such as bees and
363 wasps, their loss may be an indicator of loss of pollinators more generally and therefore be
364 predictive of economic impacts (Oliver et al., 2015). Ultimately, herbivory and pollination are
365 linked functions because the same plant species can interact with both herbivores and
366 pollinators (Sauve et al., 2015). Because *Lepidoptera* perform these critical functions within
367 ecosystems, their abundance and diversity can serve as indicators of the ability of the
368 ecosystem as a whole to provide desired functions.

369 5.2 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Ecosystem Condition

370 Invertebrates are considered by some researchers to be more powerful indicators of
371 biodiversity than vertebrates or vascular plants because they have high abundance and
372 diversity, are sensitive to perturbation, and play significant roles in ecosystems (Kazemi et al.,
373 2009a). *Lepidoptera* in particular have been identified as suitable proxies for study of

374 ecosystem functions and services because they are present in many different ecosystems and
375 are considered indicators for many groups of terrestrial insects which together make up a large
376 fraction of biodiversity (Settele et al., 2008). In addition, species cover a range of productivity,
377 their ecological functions are well known, and their short life cycles enable scientists to easily
378 observe their responses to changing conditions (WallisDeVries and van Swaay, 2017). Observed
379 changes in their abundance and diversity can be interpreted as proxies for the responses of
380 ecosystems to fluctuations in environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, water availability)
381 over shorter time scales, trends in environmental conditions due to climate change over longer
382 time scales, land use change, habitat fragmentation, and nutrient enrichment. Land use change,
383 climate change, and nitrogen deposition have been identified as key drivers of biodiversity loss
384 in general (Klop et al., 2015).

385 5.3 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Environmental Change, including Temperature and 386 Available Moisture

387 Projected impacts of climate change in temperate regions include warmer, wetter
388 winters; hotter, dryer summers; and greater inter-annual hydrologic variability (Prudencio and
389 Null, 2018). Butterflies are often regarded as benefiting from warmth, but extreme hot and dry
390 periods can decrease populations through heat stress to larvae and impacts to host plants. For
391 example, Oliver et al. (2015) documented the effect of an extreme drought event on butterfly
392 populations in England in 1995. With an understanding of population collapse and recovery in
393 response to this individual event, the authors were able to draw conclusions about long-term
394 drought impacts to butterfly populations as events of the studied magnitude are projected to
395 become more frequent in the future. For the six drought-sensitive butterfly species studied, the
396 authors concluded that the probability of the species persisting until mid-century is “around
397 zero” in the absence of emissions reductions (i.e., under CMIP5 scenario RCP8.5) and
398 adaptation measures creating and preserving habitat with suitable environmental conditions
399 (Oliver et al., 2015).

400 5.4 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Land Use Change, Habitat Fragmentation, and Climate 401 Change Impacts

402 Ecological functions of species facing fragmentation and climate change depend on
403 availability of functionally connected habitats and ability of the species to disperse quickly
404 enough to track these changes (Stevens et al., 2010). Without conscious policy to limit negative
405 impacts, urbanization results in the loss and fragmentation of preferred habitat for butterflies,
406 including loss of resources such as larval host and nectar source plants (Fenoglio et al., 2021).
407 The sizes, configurations, and locations of bioretention basins and other stormwater
408 management features potentially can play a role in limiting both habitat loss and
409 fragmentation. Butterfly species have varying abilities to adapt to fragmentation, and some are
410 examples of edge species with dispersal rates sufficient for their populations to persist as a
411 landscape becomes increasingly fragmented (Baguette et al., 2003). Butterflies are considered
412 ideal for study of spatial habitat fragmentation because their specialization makes their habitats
413 easy to map in heterogenous landscapes and because their life history characteristics are well

414 documented. In fact, dispersal is best documented in butterflies out of all animal groups
415 (Baguette and Mennechez, 2004; Stevens et al., 2010).

416 Taking action to limit habitat fragmentation is a potential strategy to help organisms
417 adapt to climate change. For example, in their projection of butterfly population responses to
418 heat and drought events, Oliver et al. (2015) considered the extent to which mitigating habitat
419 loss and fragmentation may be able to offset climate change impacts. For the six drought-
420 sensitive butterfly species studied by Oliver et al. (2015), the authors determined that measures
421 to reduce habitat loss and fragmentation could increase the probability of local persistence by
422 mid-century from near zero to 6-42% under CMIP5 scenario RCP8.5. However, they concluded
423 that emissions reductions would also be needed to increase the probability of persistence to
424 greater than 50%.

425 5.5 *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Ecological Response to Nutrient Enrichment

426 Several authors provide evidence that *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity are useful
427 indicators of nutrient enrichment impacts in ecosystems (Bobbink et al., 2010; Klop et al., 2015;
428 Pöyry et al., 2017; WallisDeVries and Swaay, 2017). The principle of reduced diversity in
429 nutrient-enriched environments begins in the soil (Poyry et al., 2017) before propagating
430 upward through trophic levels to plants (Bobbink et al., 2010) and then to insect herbivores
431 (Klop et al., 2015; Poyry et al., 2017; WallisDeVries and van Swaay, 2017). Interactions between
432 nitrogen and butterfly and moth species in engineered stormwater control measures
433 specifically have not been studied. However, a number of studies have examined the impacts of
434 agricultural and atmospheric deposition of reactive nitrogen on plant and insect communities in
435 Europe, and some parallels can be drawn to introduction of nitrogen in stormwater to
436 engineered ecosystems. Pöyry et al. (2017) studied the movement of nitrogen from
437 atmospheric deposition on soil to plants and then to 1,064 northern European butterfly and
438 moth species. Nitrogen content in plant leaves is thought to be a limiting factor for the growth
439 of insect herbivores. The authors found that nitrogen enrichment in the soil reduces plant,
440 butterfly, and moth diversity by favoring species adapted to nitrogen-rich environments (Pöyry
441 et al., 2017). Specific *Lepidoptera* traits were found to predict success of dominant butterflies
442 and moths, including a positive relationship between foliar nitrogen content and insect body
443 size, the ability to disperse widely, multivoltinism (producing multiple broods per breeding
444 season), and being either dietary generalists or specialists in consumption of plants that benefit
445 from higher-nitrogen conditions. Similarly, WallisDeVries and van Swaay (2017) and Klop et al.
446 (2015) report that by favoring some plant species over others, nitrogen deposition in natural
447 ecosystems reduces overall plant diversity and may increase insect biomass while decreasing
448 insect diversity as measured by species richness. One identified mechanism by which nutrient
449 enrichment decreases *Lepidoptera* diversity is micro-climatic cooling in the spring, when a
450 dense plant canopy can prevent temperature-sensitive caterpillars from absorbing sufficient
451 solar radiation and reaching optimal body temperatures (Klop et al., 2015). The available
452 literature makes a strong case that *Lepidoptera* abundance and diversity are useful indicators of
453 how mass and energy flows in ecosystems react to nutrient enrichment and other

454 environmental changes. Section 6 will discuss a range of existing data that can help researchers
455 quantify these ecosystem functions using *Lepidoptera*.

456 **6 Available and Relevant Data for Analysis of *Lepidoptera* as Indicators of Ecosystem** 457 **Functions**

458 A substantial amount of relevant information is available on plants recommended for
459 bioretention, on *Lepidoptera* larval host plants and habitat preferences, and on *Lepidoptera*
460 dispersal. Conditions affecting plants and *Lepidoptera* can in turn be related to more general
461 information on environmental conditions such as land use and land cover, hydrology, and water
462 quality. This information exists in databases maintained by engineering practitioners,
463 agricultural scientists, entomologists, spatial analysts, and other specialists. However, data on
464 these topics, collected and maintained by these separate disciplines, has never before been
465 connected to answer the research questions posed in this study in an urban stormwater
466 management context. Types of relevant data that can be connected to improve bioretention
467 design are summarized in Table 2. Linking plant information in engineering bioretention design
468 manuals to horticultural information provided by agricultural extension services also can be
469 useful.

470 Recommendations on plants suitable for bioretention are available in design manuals and
471 guidelines produced by state and municipal agencies and from stormwater utilities. The
472 information in these manuals can be combined with information available in U.S. federal
473 government databases such as the National Wetland Plant List (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers,
474 2020) and USDA PLANTS (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2022) database to provide extensive
475 information on the geographic occurrence and environmental tolerance ranges of plants. Links
476 between *Lepidoptera* and the presence of specific larval host plants that support them are well
477 documented and accessible in public databases (Narango et al., 2020; Robinson et al., 2023).
478 The HOSTS database combines information on caterpillar host plants from approximately 1,600
479 published and manuscript sources covering approximately 22,000 *Lepidoptera* species
480 internationally, with locations identified at the country level (Robinson et al., 2023). Narango et
481 al. (2020) used over 3,600 published sources, including HOSTS and the Biota of North America
482 Program (Kartesz, 2015), to characterize all plant genera known to occur and all *Lepidoptera*
483 species known to feed on at least one of the plant species in 83 counties across the United
484 States. For Lancaster County, Pennsylvania, for example, the data set indicates 521 plant genera
485 and 2,070 *Lepidoptera* genera present in the county. Table 3 lists ten examples of bioretention
486 plants serving as host plants for a range of *Lepidoptera* species (Narango, 2020). We chose
487 these examples to illustrate the wide range in the number of *Lepidoptera* species supported by
488 different native plants, from more than 500 to 0.

489 Data on *Lepidoptera* habitat and resource preferences is also available. The related
490 concepts of “habitat” and “resource patch” can be distinguished by spatial scale. A resource
491 patch such as a concentration of larval host plants can be delineated at the localized spatial
492 scale, while habitat can be defined as the aggregation of all resources at the landscape or
493 regional scale which collectively support an organism throughout its life cycle (Baguette and

494 Mennechez, 2004). Characterizing habitat at the landscape scale is useful because dispersal
 495 processes operate and are well documented at this scale (Stevens et al., 2010). Detailed
 496 information on larval host plants at the localized scale is not often available in urban
 497 environments, while information on land cover is widely available and can be linked logically to
 498 the habitat concept. For *Lepidoptera*, Butterflies and Moths of North America (2023) is one
 499 source describing habitat preferences. With this information, researchers can make qualitative
 500 links between spatially explicit land use/land cover information and the potential presence of
 501 specific butterfly and moth species in the landscape. The National Land Cover Database
 502 (Dewitz, 2024) provides 30 m resolution land cover information throughout the United States,
 503 and more detailed information often is available from state, municipal and regional planning
 504 agencies and from researchers. For example, high-resolution land cover information for the
 505 Chesapeake Bay and Delaware Bay watersheds in the U.S. mid-Atlantic region is available from
 506 the University of Vermont Spatial Analysis Laboratory (2016).

507 **Table 2.** Types and Example Sources of Readily Available Data that can be Connected to
 508 Improve Bioretention Design

Data Type	Example Sources
Plants suitable for bioretention	Center for Watershed Protection 2009; Prince George's County 2007; Philadelphia Water Department 2020; Shaw and Schmidt 2003; Credit Valley Conservation Authority 2010; Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District 2012
Plant characteristics and geographic occurrence	National Wetland Plant List 2020; USDA PLANTS database; Biota of North America Program; TRY database
Lepidoptera larval host plants	Narango et al. 2020; Robinson et al. 2023
Lepidoptera characteristics and habitat preferences	Butterflies and Moths of North America 2023
Lepidoptera dispersal	Stevens et al. 2010
Lepidoptera population trends	Wepprich 2019; Pelton et al. 2019; NatureServe 2023; UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme 2021; Wallis de Vries et al. 2012
Lepidoptera geographic occurrence	Global Biodiversity Information Facility; iNaturalist; museum collections
Land cover	National Land Cover Database; University of Vermont Spatial Analysis Laboratory 2016
Hydrography	National Hydrography Database; National Wetlands Inventory
Bioretention water quantity and quality	International Stormwater BMP Database
Untreated stormwater quality	Nationwide Urban Runoff Program; National Stormwater Quality Database

509

510

511

512 **Table 3.** Ten Example *Lepidoptera* Species Supported by Selected Bioretention Plants in
 513 Lancaster County, Pennsylvania (Derived from Narango, 2020)

Host Plant Scientific Name	Host Plant Genus	Host Plant Common Name	Lepidoptera Species Supported
Quercus bicolor	Quercus	swamp white oak	511
Viburnum lentago	Viburnum	nannyberry	114
Ilex verticillata	Ilex	common winterberry	43
Panicum virgatum	Panicum	switchgrass	25
Iris versicolor	Iris	harlequin blueflag	14
Asclepias incarnata	Asclepias	swamp milkweed	13
Lilium superbum	Lilium	turk's-cap lily	9
Onoclea sensibilis	Onoclea	sensitive fern	5
Oclemena nemoralis	Oclemena	bog aster	1
Echinacea purpurea	Echinacea	eastern purple coneflower	0

514

515 Ecologists have published information classifying butterfly species based on ecological
 516 characteristics or processes they participate in. These characteristics can be related to the
 517 likelihood of a particular species persisting in a given location under a given set of
 518 environmental conditions or a given change in environmental conditions, such as those brought
 519 about when a bioretention basin is added to the landscape. A simple approach to classifying
 520 species describes them as specialists or generalists in terms of habitat and food source
 521 preferences (Townsend et al., 2008). In an example of a more elaborate classification,
 522 WallisDeVries (2014) provided data on characteristics of 145 butterfly species from
 523 Northwestern Europe, grouping 16 characteristics into four components: spatial distribution
 524 and reproductive capacity (area occupied, tendency to range outside preferred habitat,
 525 individual size, potential egg production), climate conditions (moisture and temperature
 526 tolerance), generation time (growth rate of larvae, number of broods per year, overwintering
 527 ability, ability to enter diapause or a suspended developmental state), and resource
 528 specialization (territorial behavior, food and nectar plant specialization, preferred location for
 529 egg laying). For example, *Lepidoptera* that co-evolved with plants under nitrogen-limited
 530 conditions will tend to have slower larval growth rates, fewer generations per year, and less
 531 flexibility in overwintering and diapause, putting them at a disadvantage in a higher-nitrogen
 532 environment. Species with the opposite set of functional traits (e.g., faster larval growth rates)
 533 will have a competitive advantage (WallisDeVries, 2014).

534 Extensive data sets on butterfly spatial occurrence are readily available. Extensive, long-
 535 term data sets have been collected in Europe including the UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme
 536 (2021) and the Dutch Butterfly Monitoring Scheme (Wallisdevries et al., 2012). In recent years,

537 there have been substantial advances in the organization and accessibility of high-quality
538 occurrence data in repositories such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility, a portal
539 aggregating multiple databases including iNaturalist (e.g., “Pennsylvania Butterfly Species
540 Occurrence Data Set”, 2023). Butterflies are charismatic, and because they are popular with the
541 public, a large body of occurrence data is readily available from citizen scientists. With
542 appropriate consideration of uncertainty, this data can supplement high quality data collected
543 by scientists under controlled conditions, such as occurrence data documented in museum
544 collections.

545 Information on bioretention water quality and quantity and on the characteristics of urban
546 stormwater allows engineers to evaluate pollutant loads entering and leaving bioretention
547 basins, including nitrogen loads. The Nationwide Urban Runoff Program first provided high-
548 quality research data on pollutant loads in untreated urban stormwater in the United States,
549 and more recently the National Stormwater Quality Database has greatly expanded this
550 evidence by incorporating sample results submitted as part of regulatory permitting
551 requirements. The International Stormwater BMP Database is a repository for data on
552 concentrations of nitrogen and other constituents leaving bioretention basins through surface
553 flow. From these large data sets, engineers can estimate the proportion of pollutant loads that
554 are flowing through bioretention basins by surface pathways. Relevant to the goals of the
555 current study, engineers can now estimate the proportion of nitrogen reaching groundwater,
556 accumulating in bioretention soil, and being assimilated into plant tissues where it is ultimately
557 available to insect herbivores. Combining these estimates with the ecological data sets
558 mentioned throughout Section 6, it is possible to evaluate potential tradeoffs between
559 ecosystem functional objectives (for example, maximizing *Lepidoptera* diversity) and traditional
560 engineering objectives such as reducing nitrogen loads reaching downstream aquatic
561 ecosystems.

562 **7 Gaps in the Engineering Literature on Bioretention and *Lepidoptera***

563 7.1 Results of a Structured Literature Search on *Lepidoptera* and Bioretention Basins

564 To determine whether the combination of *Lepidoptera* and stormwater bioretention
565 basins has been studied in the past, a systematic keyword-based literature review was
566 conducted in line with the workflow recommended by the PRISMA 2020 protocol (Page et al.,
567 2021). The keyword search identified 62 unique records mentioning keywords related to
568 butterflies or moths in engineered stormwater control measures or constructed wetlands. After
569 examination of these records, four were determined to be relevant to the current research
570 topic (Figure 1). Bolques et al. (2010) and McCrary and Buechter (2017) are conference papers
571 making qualitative statements without providing supporting evidence. Kim (2018) reports
572 results of a field survey of plants and animals (including three species of *Lepidoptera*) following
573 installation of a rain garden in Illinois, USA. Kazemi et al. (2009a) provides quantitative results

574 and analysis for insects in stormwater bioswales in Melbourne, Australia. The study focuses on
575 ground-dwelling insects but does include some limited data on the occurrence of *Lepidoptera*.

576

577 **Figure 1.** Results of Systematic Review of Web of Science Database Conducted on May 4, 2024.
578 The literature includes over 100,000 studies of *Lepidoptera*, but the intersection of *Lepidoptera*
579 and bioretention basins for urban stormwater management has been mentioned in only four
580 studies.

581 7.2 Studies of Terrestrial Arthropods in the Melbourne Area by Kazemi et al., 2009-2011

582 In addition to Kazemi et al. (2009a) (see Section 7.1), a review of recent review and
583 synthesis studies (discussed in Section 7.3 below) identified two additional studies published by
584 the same research group, Kazemi et al. (2009b) and Kazemi et al. (2011). While these three
585 studies did not focus on *Lepidoptera*, they provided data and recommendations on the
586 intersection of bioretention-type stormwater control design and presence of a range of
587 terrestrial arthropods, including a small number of *Lepidoptera*.

588 The first of the three related studies by Kazemi (Kazemi et al., 2009a) identified the
589 presence and depth of leaf litter as an important factor in explaining arthropod biodiversity in
590 bioretention compared to lawn areas used as controls and suggested that leaf litter not be
591 removed during maintenance. In general, Kazemi et al. (2009a) hypothesized that the lesser
592 degree of human disturbance in bioretention basins compared to lawns may partially explain
593 biodiversity differences. They concluded that frequent disturbance such as mowing is likely
594 associated with decreased biodiversity. The study identified the presence of gravel in
595 bioretention basins as a positive factor for biodiversity. Drawing on past studies of natural
596 ecosystems, they hypothesized that presence of rocks and stones may provide habitat

597 heterogeneity, shelter, and suitable microhabitats for some invertebrates. The second of the
598 three studies by Kazemi (Kazemi et al., 2009b) suggested that additional factors explaining
599 greater invertebrate biodiversity in bioretention systems include a larger number of plant taxa
600 and sizes and shapes that create larger interior habitats to provide shelter from the surrounding
601 landscape.

602 The third of the three studies by Kazemi (Kazemi et al., 2011) studied the importance of
603 11 habitat factors influencing invertebrate biodiversity in nine bioswales and nine
604 corresponding “gardenbed-like” or “lawn-like” sites. They concluded that important factors
605 correlated to greater invertebrate diversity included mid-stratum vegetation (bushes, shrubs)
606 coverage, number of flowering plants, pH, and slope characteristics. The importance of shrubs
607 is consistent with findings by other researchers including Noemí Mazía et al. (2006) who
608 reported that mid-stratum vegetation can act as a keystone structure sheltering invertebrates.
609 Flowering plants support species depending on nectar. Finally, the authors found a relationship
610 between greater lateral slope (from the edge to middle of the system) and measured
611 invertebrate diversity. They suggested that the effect of slope on water ponding and soil
612 moisture creates a range of stable microclimates within the bioswale which species are able to
613 take advantage of. They further suggested that these stable microclimates may increase
614 resilience of species to climate extremes prevailing in the surrounding landscape outside the
615 bioswale, including extreme solar radiation, wind, and evaporation. These three studies are the
616 only ones available that provide specific empirical evidence specific to design of bioretention
617 basins to support invertebrates. They are briefly referenced in Pille and Säumel (2021), one of
618 four broad review and synthesis papers that will be discussed in Section 7.3.

619 7.3 Recent Review and Synthesis Studies on Green Stormwater Infrastructure and Urban 620 Ecosystems

621 To further confirm that the combined study of *Lepidoptera* and bioretention has not
622 been reported in the literature, four recent reviews and one published data set were examined,
623 each intended to synthesize a broad range of literature on urban green infrastructure and
624 ecosystem functions or services (Table 4). Prudencio and Null (2018) and Pille and Säumel
625 (2021) focused specifically on stormwater control measures, while Filazzola et al. (2019) and a
626 related data set (Filazzola et al., 2018) surveyed a wider range of urban green infrastructure
627 including some stormwater control measures. Veerkamp et al. (2021) reviewed a broad range
628 of urban green infrastructure types and a selected set of ecosystem services including
629 stormwater regulation and pollination. Of the four review and synthesis papers and one related
630 data set, only Pille and Säumel (2021) mentioned studies covering both *Lepidoptera* and
631 bioretention. The review and synthesis studies discuss a range of plant and invertebrate taxa.
632 The current study is concerned with design features supporting overall ecosystem function and

633 biodiversity, with *Lepidoptera* proposed as a key indicator but not as the only taxa of interest.
 634 For this reason, a summary of conclusions related to other taxa is provided in this section.

635 **Table 4.** Recent Review and Synthesis Studies of Green Infrastructure, Stormwater Control
 636 Measures, Habitat, Biodiversity, and Insects

Review	SCM Terms Included ¹	Number of Studies Reviewed			
		Total	Referring to SCMs and Habitat ²	Referring to Bioretention and Insect Habitat ³	Referring to Bioretention and <i>Lepidoptera</i>
Pille and Saumel, 2021	swales, ponds, rain gardens, green roofs, green walls, permeable pavement	830	140	3	3
Filazzola et al., 2018	bioswales, green roofs, retention ponds	85	25	4	0
Filazzola et al., 2019	green roofs, wetland detention basins, vegetated roadsides/bioswales	1883	59	0	0
Prudencio and Null, 2018	stormwater harvesting, stormwater capture, green roofs, basins, wells, rain barrels, wetlands, ponds, permeable pavement, permeable surfaces, pervious pavement, pervious surfaces, rain gardens, tree boxes, swales, r-tanks, underground vaults	170	48	0	0
Veerkamp et al., 2021	green roofs, rain gardens, vegetated swales, permeable surfaces, constructed wetlands, ponds	850	N/A	N/A	N/A

N/A indicates that the structure of Veerkamp et al. 2021 does not allow categorization of the studies reviewed in the same way as the other review and synthesis papers

¹ Includes references to urban stormwater control measures (SCMs).

² Includes references to urban stormwater control measures. Includes references to habitat or biodiversity.

³ Includes references to surface vegetated SCMs classified as bioretention or pseudonyms. Includes references to habitat or biodiversity. Includes references to terrestrial insects, arthropods, invertebrates, or pollinators. Papers referring only to aquatic species or mosquitoes are excluded.

637

638 While the other review and synthesis studies did not identify any studies covering both
 639 bioretention and *Lepidoptera*, they drew some conclusions relevant to design of stormwater
 640 control measures for the terrestrial ecological functions of interest. For example, the review
 641 and synthesis studies suggest that habitat and biodiversity implications of stormwater control
 642 measures have been underrepresented in the research literature relative to studies of other
 643 types of urban green infrastructure. Filazzola et al. (2019) performed a meta-analysis of
 644 published data on a range of urban green infrastructure in relation to biodiversity, covering
 645 wetland detention basins and lumping together vegetated roadsides and bioswales. The
 646 authors concluded that “[t]he effects of GI on biodiversity have been rarely quantified”.
 647 Prudencio and Null (2018) suggested that “[g]reen stormwater infrastructure could focus on
 648 biodiversity as an umbrella goal for resiliency of several ecosystem services in the urban
 649 setting.” They found that many papers referred to ecosystem services but less than 40%
 650 quantified them. Veerkamp et al. (2021), considering pollination as a proxy for biodiversity,

651 concurred that most studies to date have focused on non-stormwater features such as parks
652 and gardens.

653 A common conclusion of the review articles is that the literature on habitat and
654 stormwater control measures most comprehensively reports on green roofs and on stormwater
655 management ponds and related structures such as retention basins with permanent pools. Pille
656 and Säumel (2021) focused specifically on the intersection of stormwater control measures,
657 habitat, and biodiversity. The authors found that 85% of the studies screened provided
658 information for ponds and green roofs, while other stormwater control measures including
659 bioretention were under-represented.

660 An additional trend identified by the review articles is that ecosystem functions and
661 services are often mentioned in the literature in qualitative terms or in calls for further
662 research, but these are rarely quantified. Butterflies, insects, and pollinators are often
663 mentioned in papers in qualitative terms. Other types of insects have been quantitatively
664 studied. For example, the search revealed studies specific to dragonflies and damselflies in
665 stormwater ponds (Perron and Pick, 2020) and studies specific to mosquitoes (e.g., Hanford et
666 al., 2019).

667 Filazzola et al. (2019) examined data from 33 published studies pairing green roofs,
668 green walls, wetland detention basins, vegetated roadsides/bioswales, and yards/gardens with
669 conventional infrastructure counterparts and natural systems. The authors concluded that
670 some types of green infrastructure (green roofs and roadside bioswales but not wetland
671 detention basins or urban gardens) were found to improve biodiversity over conventional
672 counterparts in the urban environment, and in some cases were comparable to natural (non-
673 engineered) ecosystems. The authors acknowledged that the non-engineered ecosystems
674 studied tended to be urban remnants of larger ecosystems that existed historically and may
675 have retained less function than less urban, less human-impacted counterparts. The paper
676 recommended further research with experimental design frameworks that include negative
677 controls (conventionally designed urban infrastructure), positive controls, (“natural” or non-
678 engineered ecosystems), replication, and sufficient sample sizes to draw formal statistical
679 inferences.

680 The review and synthesis articles identify a trend in the literature calling for further
681 research on the role stormwater management measures have in fostering habitat connectivity
682 at the landscape scale. For example, Pille and Säumel (2021) recommended increasing the
683 number and density of stormwater control measures designed specifically to support
684 biodiversity to increase the overall quality and connectivity of urban green infrastructure. They
685 also recommend focusing these efforts specifically on identified corridors for animal
686 movement. A frequent recommendation for further study found is to consider not only the
687 local scale of individual stormwater or green infrastructure facilities, but also their larger
688 landscape context including the distribution of resources spatially and the ability of organisms
689 to move and disperse between habitat areas (e.g., Kremen et al., 2007). Researchers (e.g.,
690 McDermott Long et al., 2017) also suggest that mitigating habitat fragmentation effects may be

691 a way to reduce downward pressure on species populations caused by gradual increases in
 692 mean temperature and by increases in the frequency and severity of extreme climate events.
 693 The review and synthesis studies identify recent research on green roofs, insects, and habitat
 694 connectivity at a landscape scale in urban areas (Brenneisen, 2006; Gonsalves et al., 2022;
 695 Wooster et al., 2022). Some research methods employed in these studies may be transferrable
 696 to bioretention studies.

697 Table 5 summarizes planning, design, and maintenance recommendations found
 698 through the structured literature review. Recommendations include increasing the number and
 699 density of bioretention basins designed to enhance biodiversity within the landscape, siting
 700 basins to reduce landscape-scale fragmentation and enhance animal movement, incorporating
 701 physical features that create heterogeneous habitat and moisture conditions within basins,
 702 maximizing plant diversity and flowering plants, and minimizing human disturbance.

703 **Table 5.** Summary of Planning and Design Recommendations in the Literature to Provide
 704 Habitat and Increase Biodiversity of Insects in Bioretention Basins

Source	Category	Recommendation
Pille and Saumel, 2021	Planning/Siting	Increase number and density of stormwater controls designed to enhance biodiversity.
Kremen et al., 2007; Pille and Saumel, 2021	Planning/Siting	Place stormwater controls designed to enhance biodiversity within identified animal movement corridors.
McDermott et al., 2017	Planning/Siting	Place stormwater controls to help mitigate habitat fragmentation at the landscape scale.
Kazemi et al., 2009a	Design	Incorporate gravel, rocks, and stones.
Kazemi et al., 2009b, 2011; Noemi Mazia, 2006	Design	Maximize the number of plant taxa and the number of flowering plants. Include mid-stratum vegetation (bushes, shrubs).
Kazemi et al., 2009b	Design	Configure size and shape to maximize interior habitat.
Kazemi et al., 2011	Design	Configure slope to create a gradient of moisture conditions.
Kazemi et al., 2009a	Maintenance	Do not remove leaf litter.
Kazemi et al., 2009a	Maintenance	Minimize mowing and other forms of disturbance.

705

706 **8 Conclusions: An Agenda for Engineering Research and Action**

707 We have suggested a relatively simple framework for improving ecological outcomes of
 708 engineering designs based on plant choice and *Lepidoptera* larva supported by those plants.
 709 Since terrestrial ecosystem function has in most cases not been considered at all in typical
 710 engineering bioretention design practice, we believe simply choosing larval host plants for
 711 *Lepidoptera* that are suitable for environmental conditions will immediately improve outcomes
 712 compared to current practice. We acknowledge that this proposed approach does not consider
 713 all the complex temporal and spatial ecosystem dynamics that occur in bioretention basins.
 714 There are many more questions that can be explored at the intersection of bioretention
 715 engineering and ecology. Drawing from this detailed literature review, we propose a series of

716 questions for future research. While further research will certainly improve scientific
717 understanding, an overarching question is whether considering additional ecological complexity
718 within bioretention basins will improve engineering design decisions leading to more desirable
719 outcomes. For new research to improve ecosystem functional outcomes of bioretention
720 designs, research findings must inform bioretention engineering practice. This section therefore
721 concludes with some ideas for applying research outcomes to the professional practice of
722 bioretention design. Table 6 summarizes the recommendations made in Section 8.

723

724 **Table 6.** Recommendations for Future Research and Applications to Professional Practice

Section	Category	Topic	Question or Recommendation
8.1.1	Future Research	Tradeoffs	Does meeting water regulation and pollutant load objectives place limits on ecological functions that can be achieved in and around bioretention basins?
8.1.2	Future Research	Microclimates	Can attention to microclimates in design improve ecosystem functions?
8.1.3	Future Research	Temporal Dynamics	Is detailed consideration of ecosystem temporal dynamics necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?
8.1.4	Future Research	Stochastic Processes	Is detailed consideration of stochastic processes affecting species occurrence necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?
8.1.5	Future Research	Spatiotemporal Dynamics	Is detailed consideration of dispersal, migration, and population dynamics in both space and time necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?
8.1.6	Future Research	Climate Change	Will climate change degrade ecosystem functions in and around bioretention basins, and can design choices mitigate this degradation?
8.1.7	Future Research	Pollination	Can the presence of Lepidoptera host plants serve as an effective proxy for pollination?
8.1.8	Future Research	Connectivity	Can bioretention basins serve as part of a larger green infrastructure network to create an urbanized landscape with improved terrestrial ecological functions?
8.1.9	Future Research	Watershed Scale	Is a similar scale of bioretention implementation needed to achieve both hydrologic and ecological objectives?
8.1.10	Future Research	Ecosystem Services	Does valuing ecosystem functions in financial units improve design decisions and outcomes?
8.2.1	Application	Decision Support Tools	Use evidence produced by research to inform decision support tools for bioretention planners and designers.
8.2.2	Application	Design Guidelines	Use evidence produced by research to inform bioretention design guidelines used in professional practice.
8.2.3	Application	Standard Plans, Details, Specifications	Use evidence produced by research to inform bioretention plans, details, and technical specifications used in professional practice.
8.2.4	Application	Maintenance Protocols	Use evidence produced by research to inform bioretention maintenance protocols.
8.2.5	Application	Model Codes and Ordinances	Use evidence produced by research to inform codes governing land use and design on private property.
8.2.6	Application	Other Policy Options	Consider how evidence produced by research can inform innovative policy options to support urban ecosystem functions and biodiversity.

726

727 8.1 Key Research Questions

728 8.1.1 Do the hydrologic and biogeochemical conditions necessary to meet traditional
729 engineering performance objectives place limits on habitat provision, biodiversity, and
730 pollination that can be achieved in and around bioretention basins? Put another way, are
731 tradeoffs required between traditional engineering performance objectives and terrestrial
732 ecosystem objectives? Are there specific design choices that can minimize these tradeoffs?

733 While design professionals may be interested in adding terrestrial ecosystem objectives
734 such as habitat provision to their design frameworks, most projects will continue to have
735 minimum requirements for traditional criteria including peak outflow rate control, groundwater
736 recharge, and export of pollutants to downstream aquatic ecosystems. Many of these design
737 guidelines and regulatory requirements are aimed at protection of human life, property, and
738 integrity of downstream aquatic ecosystems. Meeting these minimum legal requirements
739 typically is not negotiable, and project stakeholders may wish to exceed minimum
740 requirements in some situations. Therefore, a useful outcome of future research will be to
741 better describe and quantify any tradeoffs between maximization of terrestrial ecosystem
742 functions and these traditional water resource engineering objectives. This paper has argued
743 that the mix of plants present in a bioretention basin, particularly larval host plants for
744 *Lepidoptera*, is a suitable indicator of potential biodiversity and ecosystem function that can
745 develop in the basin. If critical larval host plants are not able to survive in the basin, this may
746 place an upper limit on potential ecosystem function. Design choices including bioretention
747 system surface area, maximum surface ponding volume, and engineered soil depth govern the
748 hydroperiod and time pattern of soil moisture in bioretention systems. These patterns place
749 bounds on the range of plants that can be grown in a given system.

750 Concentrated resource inputs such as nutrients have been shown to result in lower-
751 diversity ecosystems, and a goal of engineered bioretention systems is to intercept and process
752 these excess resources before they reach downstream aquatic ecosystems. Eutrophic
753 conditions in ecosystems have been shown to reduce biodiversity in the soil, among plants, and
754 upward through the food chain to herbivores including *Lepidoptera*. If keystone larval host
755 plants are unable to survive or compete in the nutrient-rich conditions expected in bioretention
756 basins, it is reasonable to expect that this may result in unavoidable tradeoffs between nutrient
757 processing and biodiversity support functions of the systems.

758 The range of plants that can persist in a bioretention basin may be limited by additional
759 factors such as the presence of deicing salts, other toxins, or development and persistence of
760 low-oxygen conditions if unexpected soil or hydraulic conditions lead to prolonged saturation.

761 Further research can explore whether plants that can persist in these conditions are able to also
762 provide habitat, support herbivores, and support pollinators.

763 8.1.2 Can attention to microclimates in design improve ecosystem functions?

764 Literature sources reviewed suggest that design choices can intentionally create
765 microclimates creating a variety of environmental conditions within a bioretention basin, and
766 that this variety in microclimates can then support greater biodiversity. Examples of these
767 design choices include incorporating a variety of plant sizes (grasses, shrubs, trees);
768 incorporating a variety of flowering plants; including gravel, rocks, and stones; creating larger
769 interior habitats to provide shelter from extremes of wind, temperature, and solar radiation in
770 the surrounding landscape; creating lateral slopes (from the edge to center of the basin) that
771 provide a gradient of soil moisture conditions; and minimizing disturbance as much as practical
772 to leave leaf litter in place. Empirical testing of these hypotheses can help inform future
773 designs.

774 8.1.3 Is detailed understanding and consideration of ecosystem temporal dynamics
775 necessary to achieve desired design outcomes?

776 The discussion in this paper to this point has largely neglected temporal dynamics of
777 urban ecosystems. Plant succession can occur over short time scales, particularly in newly
778 established or disturbed ecosystems like bioretention basins. To some extent, changes in
779 engineered ecosystems such as bioretention basins can be managed by standardized operation
780 and maintenance activities. These activities may include removal of undesirable plant species
781 and replanting or supplementing of desirable ones. Nonetheless, competition and succession
782 processes can be expected to establish trends in the species assemblage present in a given
783 system over time. Arrival and spread of invasive species is another temporal process that will
784 affect species assemblage. Episodic extreme heat, cold, wet weather, drought, and human
785 intervention can further favor species that are more resistant and resilient to disturbances.

786 Seasonal dynamics are additional examples of temporal dynamics that potentially can
787 be considered in design. One example of a seasonal dynamic is the timing of blooms serving as
788 nectar sources for different species of pollinators over the course of a year. Another example is
789 the timing of insect overwintering relative to increases in heat, light, and predation in the spring
790 (e.g., Stevens et al., 2018). Climate change may tend to result in mismatches between historical
791 seasonal patterns and the timing of animal and plant activity, termed phenological asynchrony.
792 These mismatches may put downward pressure on the populations of some species (Donoso et
793 al., 2016). A final example is the timing of deicing chemical application in colder urbanized
794 regions, the timing of spring rainfall that tends to flush these substances from soil into

795 groundwater and surface water, and the beginning of the spring growing season for plant
796 species that are sensitive to these chemicals (e.g., Shetty et al., 2020).

797 8.1.4 Is it necessary to account for the probability of dispersal and animal movement, or
798 is a framework based on theoretical carrying capacity sufficient to achieve design outcomes?

799 The concepts presented in this paper consider the theoretical carrying capacity of
800 ecosystems under a given set of physical conditions. Chance also plays a role in determining
801 whether organisms that can be supported by the physical conditions in a given basin are
802 actually present in a given place and time. Interdisciplinary collaboration with biologists can
803 design and execute experimental designs to confirm the validity of predictions made on the
804 basis of theoretical carrying capacity. Researchers have suggested that field experimental
805 designs should incorporate positive controls (analogous ecosystems with minimal human
806 disturbance), negative controls (“business as usual” urban designs), replication, and sufficient
807 sample sizes to support formal statistical inferences. A practical objective of this research can
808 be to determine whether accounting for the empirical presence of organisms would change the
809 optimal decisions of design professionals.

810 8.1.5 To what extent is it necessary to consider the complexities of *Lepidopteran*
811 dispersal processes, migration, and population dynamics in both space and time in order to
812 inform successful design decisions?

813 Ultimately, spatial habitat connectivity is linked to the temporal processes of organism
814 arrival, dispersal, localized extinction, and other population dynamics. The abundance and
815 distribution of migratory species, such as the monarch butterfly, depends on processes playing
816 out over even larger spatial scales. Interdisciplinary research can explore whether accounting
817 for these dynamics in the engineering design process would improve design decision making or
818 lead to more desirable design outcomes that encourage butterfly usage.

819 8.1.6 Will climate change further decrease maximum terrestrial ecosystem function that
820 can be achieved in and around bioretention basins? If so, can specific design decisions increase
821 climate change resilience of the bioretention systems and surrounding ecosystems?

822 An important area of research will be to determine whether conclusions about any
823 tradeoffs between water management, habitat provision and support for greater biodiversity
824 will continue to hold as climate change modifies environmental conditions, potentially moving
825 them outside the range favored by plants and animals currently inhabiting a given geographic
826 area. Climate change also is expected to affect local environmental conditions by modifying the
827 frequency, magnitude, and duration of precipitation and dry periods, leading to changes in the
828 frequency distribution of inundation and soil moisture within the root zone of plants. Climate
829 change is affecting and will continue to affect the frequency of extreme events including heat,
830 cold, storms, fires, and floods. These modified conditions may affect the ability of preferred
831 larval host and nectar source plants to persist, indirectly affecting *Lepidoptera* and organisms at
832 higher trophic levels. Modified conditions such as higher temperatures also may affect
833 *Lepidoptera*, birds, and other species directly. Gradual trends introduced by climate change can

834 further affect the outcome of competition and succession processes over time. It may be
835 necessary to choose plants able to tolerate longer drought periods while still supporting
836 herbivores and pollinators.

837 8.1.7 Can potential *Lepidoptera* diversity estimated from larval host plants serve as an
838 effective proxy for pollination in the urban ecosystem?

839 The discussion in this paper has focused on providing conditions conducive to increasing
840 the abundance and diversity of insect herbivores, with a particular focus on *Lepidoptera*. It was
841 hypothesized that designing to support herbivores will indirectly support pollinators, including
842 bees. We acknowledge that bees are dominant pollinators of many wild plants and
843 economically important crops. The hypothesis that *Lepidoptera*-based indicators may be an
844 adequate proxy for urban pollination remains to be tested, and research on pollination could
845 complement the research on herbivore functions discussed in this paper. Documented
846 interactions between insects and specific nectar source plants also could be taken into account
847 more explicitly in future research.

848 8.1.8 Can planners and designers use bioretention basins as part of a larger green
849 infrastructure network to create an urbanized landscape with improved terrestrial ecological
850 functions? How much does location of bioretention basins matter relative to the total habitat
851 area they represent? What spatial metrics best capture city-scale connectivity and how much
852 bioretention needs to be implemented to significantly improve the values of these metrics?

853 The realized abundance and diversity of *Lepidoptera* and other species at the urban site
854 scale will not be determined in isolation but will depend on the abundance, diversity, and
855 movement of species at the larger city and watershed scales. A future research agenda can take
856 this interplay of spatial scales into account. Of interest are interplay between stormwater
857 management elements (including bioretention-like practices, green roofs, ponds, wetlands and
858 detention/retention basins) and other urban green infrastructure elements such as street and
859 landscaping trees (the urban forest); larger parks and institutional landscapes (e.g., education,
860 health care, government campuses); and roadside vegetation. Trees and other large woody
861 plants are ecologically important but not always practical in stormwater management practices
862 in highly urban environments. On the other hand, stormwater management practices may be
863 able to take advantage of the water-rich environment to provide nectar and larval host plant
864 species that would not otherwise be present in the urban environment. A strategy at the larger
865 spatial scale may be able to take advantage of these opportunities afforded by stormwater
866 elements and the biodiversity-supporting power of trees to create an overall landscape that
867 maximizes biological diversity and abundance while also meeting hydrologic objectives and
868 minimum legal requirements for water resources management.

869 At an even larger scale, Derby Lewis et al. (2019) and Hall et al. (2017) suggest a role for
870 urban green infrastructure in providing refuges and movement corridors for wildlife surrounded

871 by intensively agricultural landscapes. Future research could further explore the role green
872 stormwater infrastructure specifically can play within such a regional framework.

873 8.1.9 Is the magnitude of bioretention implementation needed to achieve desired urban
874 hydrological and other ecosystem functions at the city scale similar to the magnitude needed at
875 the watershed scale? Do tradeoffs exist at this larger scale or can both sets of objectives be
876 maximized?

877 To achieve traditional engineering water resources management objectives such as peak
878 flow reduction, hydrologic cycle management, and pollutant load management in urban areas,
879 implementation of management features must achieve a minimum threshold relative to the
880 scale of the watershed. For example, in an urbanized (48% impervious surfaces) watershed in
881 Philadelphia, Kwak et al. (2024) documented decreases in the frequency of peak streamflow at
882 the watershed scale with surface runoff from approximately 5% of the impervious cover
883 managed by bioretention and other stormwater management measures. Based on studies of
884 benthic macroinvertebrate and fish communities, researchers have suggested that when an
885 urbanizing watershed surpasses a threshold on the order of 10% of the land surface covered by
886 impervious surfaces without effective stormwater management, downstream aquatic
887 ecosystem function begins to be adversely affected (Schueler et al., 2009). Once an
888 understanding is reached of the scale of green infrastructure implementation required to
889 achieve terrestrial ecosystem function objectives in urban environments, along with an
890 understanding of the required scale and role of green stormwater infrastructure specifically
891 within that larger network, an interesting research endeavor will be to explore whether this
892 threshold is similar to the threshold of implementation required to achieve watershed-scale
893 hydrologic and water quality objectives.

894 8.1.10 Does making the connection from ecosystem functions to ecosystem (economic)
895 services improve design outcomes?

896 This paper has focused on ecosystem functions of bioretention basins and stopped short
897 of linking these explicitly to ecosystem services, or the benefits that ecosystem functions
898 provide to humans. Some authors in the engineering and planning literature do not clearly
899 distinguish between the terms functions and services, and making this clear distinction is
900 recommended. For example, the ecosystem services framework considered by Prudencio and
901 Null (2018) included improved water quality, groundwater replenishment, recreation
902 opportunities, “creation of diverse habitats”, ability to “counter impacts from urbanization
903 while also increasing natural capacity to buffer for anticipated climate change”, and carbon
904 sequestration as services. There is much fundamental research that can be conducted on
905 ecosystem functions before they are tied to the economic concept of services, whether or not
906 these services are ultimately valued in currency units. Nonetheless, tying functions to services
907 may open up decision making approaches rooted in economics, such as benefit-cost analysis.
908 These frameworks can be useful to inform policy and design decisions about where to invest
909 limited financial and other resources for maximum benefit. It is suggested that engineers
910 involved in this type of research collaborate with economists and other professionals with

911 economic benefits valuation expertise, whether or not these benefits are ultimately valued in
912 currency terms.

913 8.2 Connecting Research and Engineering Practice

914 Engineers have an ethical responsibility to make choices for the good of the public and
915 of the environment. The choices of engineers and other professionals working in urban
916 environments have potential to either mitigate or exacerbate drivers of insect decline.
917 Engineers make daily decisions about the built environment and infrastructure of cities - what is
918 going to be built, how it will be sized and configured, and what materials it will be composed of.
919 Water resources engineers make decisions that affect the quantity and quality of runoff from
920 urban surfaces. Water resources engineers collaborate with landscape architects, biologists,
921 and other professionals on soil and plant choices for stormwater management practices. These
922 decisions may be formalized for use on many projects through documents such as decision
923 support tools, design guidelines, standard plans and details, master technical specifications,
924 planting plans, and standard operating protocols for maintenance (e.g., Zare et al., 2024).

925 Urban planners and managers at government agencies such as transportation
926 departments and water utilities also make policy decisions that affect the composition of the
927 urban environment at the watershed scale over time. Agencies may have direct control over
928 where stormwater management practices are constructed on public property. Large
929 institutional land owners such as universities have similar control. The composition of the urban
930 environment also is affected over time by the content of regulations affecting private
931 development such as municipal stormwater ordinances, zoning codes, and building codes.
932 Taken together, incorporating refined guidance such as recommended plant choices in these
933 documents represents an opportunity to direct the course of the urban built environment in a
934 direction that will maintain or restore both hydrological and ecological functions. A large
935 number of small choices made daily by professionals with some influence over site-scale design
936 and watershed-scale land use policy can add up to big change over time.

937 8.3 Overall Conclusions

938 We have identified a significant opportunity to close a gap in knowledge and
939 collaboration between the fields of engineering and ecology. By connecting existing knowledge
940 available within these fields and applying the results to engineering design, bioretention basins
941 can be transformed into more functional elements within urban ecosystems while still
942 providing core water quantity and quality management functions. This result has important
943 policy implications for professionals working to find solutions to intertwined water
944 management and ecological challenges facing urban areas.

945

946

947 **Acknowledgments**

948 We would like to thank Villanova University, the College of Engineering, and the Department of
949 Civil and Environmental Engineering for providing funding to support completion and
950 publication of this research.

951

952 **Open Research**

953 All data referred to in this study are publicly available. Each data set cited in the text is linked to a
954 corresponding reference including a Digital Object Identifier when available or a URL and access date.

955

956 **References**

957 Almond, R. E. A., Grooten, M., Juffe Bignoli, D., & Petersen, T. (2022). Living Planet Report 2022
958 – Building a nature-positive society. World Wildlife Fund (WWF) and Zoological Society of
959 London. Retrieved from <http://stats.livingplanetindex.org/>

960

961 Baguette, M., & Mennechez, G. (2004). Resource and habitat patches, landscape ecology and
962 metapopulation biology: a consensual viewpoint. *Oikos*, 106(2), 399–403.
963 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0030-1299.2004.13120.x>

964

965 Baguette, M., Mennechez, G., Petit, S., & Schtickzelle, N. (2003). Effect of habitat fragmentation
966 on dispersal in the butterfly *Proclissiana eunomia*. *Comptes Rendus. Biologies*, 326(S1), 200–
967 209. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1631-0691\(03\)00058-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1631-0691(03)00058-1)

968

969 Beyers, R. J., & Odum, H. T. (1993). *Ecological Microcosms*. New York, NY: Springer New York.
970 <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-9344-3>

971

972 Bobbink, R., Hicks, K., Galloway, J., Spranger, T., Alkemade, R., Ashmore, M., et al. (2010).
973 Global assessment of nitrogen deposition effects on terrestrial plant diversity: a synthesis.
974 *Ecological Applications*, 20(1), 30–59. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-1140.1>

975

976 Bolques, A., Cherrier, J., Abazinge, M., & Matungwa, G. (2010). Installation of a
977 Bioretention/Rain Garden to Mitigate Agricultural Irrigation Runoff from a Container Plant
978 Nursery. In *Proceedings of the Florida State Horticultural Society*. Retrieved from
979 <https://journals.flvc.org/fshs/article/download/86813/83728>

980

- 981 Bratieres, K., Fletcher, T. D., Deletic, A., & Zinger, Y. (2008). Nutrient and sediment removal by
982 stormwater biofilters: A large-scale design optimisation study. *Water Research*, 42(14), 3930–
983 3940. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2008.06.009>
984
- 985 Brenneisen, S. (2006). Space for urban wildlife: Designing green roofs as habitats in Switzerland.
986 *Urban Habitats*, 4(1), 27–36.
987
- 988 Burton, Jr., G. Allen, & Pitt, R. (2001). *Stormwater Effects Handbook: A Toolbox for Watershed*
989 *Managers, Scientists, and Engineers* (0 ed.). CRC Press.
990 <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420036244>
991
- 992 Butterflies and Moths of North America. (2023, April 30). Retrieved from
993 <http://www.butterfliesandmoths.org>
994
- 995 Center for Watershed Protection and Maryland Department of the Environment. (2009).
996 *Maryland Stormwater Design Manual Volumes I & II. Appendix A: Landscaping Guidance for*
997 *Stormwater BMPs*. Retrieved from
998 [https://mde.maryland.gov/programs/water/StormwaterManagementProgram/Pages/stormwa](https://mde.maryland.gov/programs/water/StormwaterManagementProgram/Pages/stormwater_design.aspx)
999 [ter_design.aspx](https://mde.maryland.gov/programs/water/StormwaterManagementProgram/Pages/stormwater_design.aspx)
1000
- 1001 Chao, A., Gotelli, N. J., Hsieh, T. C., Sander, E. L., Ma, K. H., Colwell, R. K., & Ellison, A. M. (2014).
1002 Rarefaction and extrapolation with Hill numbers: a framework for sampling and estimation in
1003 species diversity studies. *Ecological Monographs*, 84(1), 45–67. [https://doi.org/10.1890/13-](https://doi.org/10.1890/13-0133.1)
1004 [0133.1](https://doi.org/10.1890/13-0133.1)
1005
- 1006 Chaves, M. T. R., Farias, T. R. L., & Eloi, W. M. (2024). Comparative analysis of bioretention
1007 design strategies for urban runoff infiltration: a critical overview. *Ecological Engineering*, 207,
1008 107352. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2024.107352>
1009
- 1010 Concepción, E. D., Moretti, M., Altermatt, F., Nobis, M. P., & Obrist, M. K. (2015). Impacts of
1011 urbanisation on biodiversity: the role of species mobility, degree of specialisation and spatial
1012 scale. *Oikos*, 124(12), 1571–1582. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.02166>
1013
- 1014 Cook, L. M., Good, K. D., Moretti, M., Kremer, P., Wadzuk, B., Traver, R., & Smith, V. (2023).
1015 Towards the intentional, multifunctional design of green infrastructure.
1016 <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-14044>
1017
- 1018 Correa Ayram, C. A., Mendoza, M. E., Etter, A., & Salicrup, D. R. P. (2016). Habitat connectivity
1019 in biodiversity conservation: A review of recent studies and applications. *Progress in Physical*
1020 *Geography: Earth and Environment*, 40(1), 7–37. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309133315598713>
1021
- 1022 Costanza, R., d'Arge, R., De Groot, R., Farber, S., Grasso, M., Hannon, B., et al. (1997). The value
1023 of the world's ecosystem services and natural capital. *Nature*, 387(6630), 253–260.
1024 <https://doi.org/10.1038/387253a0>

- 1025
1026 Credit Valley Conservation Authority (2010). Low Impact Development Stormwater
1027 Management Planning and Design Guide (LID Guide), Version 1.0. Appendix B - Landscape
1028 Design Guide for Low Impact Development.
1029
1030 Dagenais, D., Brisson, J., & Fletcher, T. D. (2018). The role of plants in bioretention systems;
1031 does the science underpin current guidance? *Ecological Engineering*, 120, 532–545.
1032 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2018.07.007>
1033
1034 Davis, A. P., Hunt, W. F., & Traver, R. (2022). *Green stormwater infrastructure fundamentals*
1035 *and design*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
1036
1037 Debo, T. N., & Reese, A. (2002). *Municipal Stormwater Management* (0 ed.). CRC Press.
1038 <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781420032260>
1039
1040 Derby Lewis, A., Bouman, M. J., Winter, A. M., Hasle, E. A., Stotz, D. F., Johnston, M. K., et al.
1041 (2019). Does Nature Need Cities? Pollinators Reveal a Role for Cities in Wildlife Conservation.
1042 *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 7, 220. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2019.00220>
1043
1044 Dewitz, Jon. (2024). National Land Cover Database (NLCD) 2019 Products (ver. 3.0, February
1045 2024) [Data set]. U.S. Geological Survey. <https://doi.org/10.5066/P9KZCM54>
1046
1047 Dirzo, R., Young, H. S., Galetti, M., Ceballos, G., Isaac, N. J. B., & Collen, B. (2014). Defaunation in
1048 the Anthropocene. *Science*, 345(6195), 401–406. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1251817>
1049
1050 Donoso, I., Stefanescu, C., Martínez-Abraín, A., & Traveset, A. (2016). Phenological asynchrony
1051 in plant-butterfly interactions associated with climate: a community-wide perspective. *Oikos*,
1052 125(10), 1434–1444. <https://doi.org/10.1111/oik.03053>
1053
1054 European Commission. Directorate General for Environment. (2021). *EU biodiversity strategy*
1055 *for 2030: bringing nature back into our lives*. LU: Publications Office. Retrieved from
1056 <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/677548>
1057
1058 Fenoglio, M. S., Calviño, A., González, E., Salvo, A., & Videla, M. (2021). Urbanisation drivers and
1059 underlying mechanisms of terrestrial insect diversity loss in cities. *Ecological Entomology*, 46(4),
1060 757–771. <https://doi.org/10.1111/een.13041>
1061
1062 Filazzola, A., Maclvor, J. S., & Shrestha, N. (2018). A systematic review of green infrastructure
1063 effects on urban ecosystems [Text/xml]. [object Object]. <https://doi.org/10.5063/F1S180S8>
1064
1065 Filazzola, A., Shrestha, N., & Maclvor, J. S. (2019). The contribution of constructed green
1066 infrastructure to urban biodiversity: A synthesis and meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*,
1067 56(9), 2131–2143. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13475>
1068

- 1069 Forister, M. L., Pelton, E. M., & Black, S. H. (2019). Declines in insect abundance and diversity:
1070 We know enough to act now. *Conservation Science and Practice*, 1(8).
1071 <https://doi.org/10.1111/csp2.80>
1072
- 1073 Giannetti, B. F., Marcilio, M. D. F. D. F. B., Coscieme, L., Agostinho, F., Liu, G., & Almeida, C. M.
1074 V. B. (2019). Howard Odum's "Self-organization, transformity and information": Three decades
1075 of empirical evidence. *Ecological Modelling*, 407, 108717.
1076 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2019.06.005>
1077
- 1078 Gonsalves, S., Starry, O., Szallies, A., & Brenneisen, S. (2022). Correction to: The effect of urban
1079 green roof design on beetle biodiversity. *Urban Ecosystems*, 25(1), 221–221.
1080 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11252-021-01155-x>
1081
- 1082 Goulson, D. (2021). *Silent earth: averting the insect apocalypse* (First U.S. edition). New York,
1083 NY: Harper, an imprint of HarperCollinsPublishers.
1084
- 1085 Habel, J. C., Samways, M. J., & Schmitt, T. (2019). Mitigating the precipitous decline of
1086 terrestrial European insects: Requirements for a new strategy. *Biodiversity and Conservation*,
1087 28(6), 1343–1360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-019-01741-8>
1088
- 1089 Hall, D. M., Camilo, G. R., Tonietto, R. K., Ollerton, J., Ahrné, K., Arduser, M., et al. (2017). The
1090 city as a refuge for insect pollinators: Insect Pollinators. *Conservation Biology*, 31(1), 24–29.
1091 <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12840>
1092
- 1093 Halsch, C. A., Shapiro, A. M., Fordyce, J. A., Nice, C. C., Thorne, J. H., Waetjen, D. P., & Forister,
1094 M. L. (2021). Insects and recent climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of*
1095 *Sciences*, 118(2), e2002543117. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2002543117>
1096
- 1097 Hanford, J. K., Webb, C. E., & Hochuli, D. F. (2019). Habitat Traits Associated with Mosquito Risk
1098 and Aquatic Diversity in Urban Wetlands. *Wetlands*, 39(4), 743–758.
1099 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13157-019-01133-2>
1100
- 1101 Harvey, J. A., Tougeron, K., Gols, R., Heinen, R., Abarca, M., Abram, P. K., et al. (2023). Scientists'
1102 warning on climate change and insects. *Ecological Monographs*, 93(1), e1553.
1103 <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecm.1553>
1104
- 1105 Hsieh, C., Davis, A. P., & Needelman, B. A. (2007). Nitrogen Removal from Urban Stormwater
1106 Runoff Through Layered Bioretention Columns. *Water Environment Research*, 79(12), 2404–
1107 2411. <https://doi.org/10.2175/106143007X183844>
1108
- 1109 Jani, J., Yang, Y.-Y., Lusk, M. G., & Toor, G. S. (2020). Composition of nitrogen in urban
1110 residential stormwater runoff: Concentrations, loads, and source characterization of nitrate and
1111 organic nitrogen. *PLOS ONE*, 15(2), e0229715. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229715>
1112

- 1113 Janousek, W. M., Douglas, M. R., Cannings, S., Clément, M. A., Delphia, C. M., Everett, J. G., et
1114 al. (2023). Recent and future declines of a historically widespread pollinator linked to climate,
1115 land cover, and pesticides. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(5),
1116 e2211223120. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2211223120>
1117
- 1118 Jax, K. (2005). Function and “functioning” in ecology: what does it mean? *Oikos*, 111(3), 641–
1119 648. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1600-0706.2005.13851.x>
1120
- 1121 Kartesz, J. T. (2015). The Biota of North America Program: North American Vascular Flora
1122 (Version 1.0) [Data set]. Retrieved from <http://www.bonap.org/>
1123
- 1124 Kazemi, F., Beecham, S., Gibbs, J., & Clay, R. (2009). Factors affecting terrestrial invertebrate
1125 diversity in bioretention basins in an Australian urban environment. *Landscape and Urban*
1126 *Planning*, 92(3–4), 304–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2009.05.014>
1127
- 1128 Kazemi, F., Beecham, S., & Gibbs, J. (2009). Streetscale bioretention basins in Melbourne and
1129 their effect on local biodiversity. *Ecological Engineering*, 35(10), 1454–1465.
1130 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2009.06.003>
1131
- 1132 Kazemi, F., Beecham, S., & Gibbs, J. (2011). Streetscape biodiversity and the role of bioretention
1133 swales in an Australian urban environment. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 101(2), 139–148.
1134 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2011.02.006>
1135
- 1136 Kim, J. (2018). Exploring green infrastructure benefits at house and neighborhood scale: case
1137 study of Illinois, USA. *Landscape and Ecological Engineering*, 14(1), 165–174.
1138 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11355-017-0331-0>
1139
- 1140 Klop, E., Omon, B., & WallisDeVries, M. F. (2015). Impact of nitrogen deposition on larval
1141 habitats: the case of the Wall Brown butterfly *Lasiommata megera*. *Journal of Insect*
1142 *Conservation*, 19(2), 393–402. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10841-014-9748-z>
1143
- 1144 Kremen, C., Williams, N. M., Aizen, M. A., Gemmill-Herren, B., LeBuhn, G., Minckley, R., et al.
1145 (2007). Pollination and other ecosystem services produced by mobile organisms: a conceptual
1146 framework for the effects of land-use change. *Ecology Letters*, 10(4), 299–314.
1147 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2007.01018.x>
1148
- 1149 Kurze, S., Heinken, T., & Fartmann, T. (2018). Nitrogen enrichment in host plants increases the
1150 mortality of common *Lepidoptera* species. *Oecologia*, 188(4), 1227–1237.
1151 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-018-4266-4>
1152
- 1153 Lucas, W. C., & Greenway, M. (2011). Hydraulic Response and Nitrogen Retention in
1154 Bioretention Mesocosms with Regulated Outlets: Part I-Hydraulic Response. *Water*
1155 *Environment Research*, 83(8), 692–702. <https://doi.org/10.2175/106143010X12780288628697>

- 1156 McCrary, S. M., & Buechter, M. T. (2017). Get the Rain Out Together: MSD Rainscaping Small
1157 Grants Program. In World Environmental and Water Resources Congress 2017. Retrieved from
1158 <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/9780784480632.036>
1159
- 1160 McDermott Long, O., Warren, R., Price, J., Brereton, T. M., Botham, M. S., & Franco, A. M. A.
1161 (2017). Sensitivity of UK butterflies to local climatic extremes: which life stages are most at risk?
1162 *Journal of Animal Ecology*, 86(1), 108–116. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2656.12594>
1163
- 1164 Metropolitan St. Louis Sewer District (2012). Landscape Guide for Stormwater Best
1165 Management Practice Design (Rev. 2). Retrieved from
1166 https://www.cityoffrontenac.org/egov/documents/1460670982_18428.PDF
1167
- 1168 Narango, D. L., Tallamy, D. W., & Shropshire, K. J. (2020). Few keystone plant genera support
1169 the majority of *Lepidoptera* species. *Nature Communications*, 11(1), 5751.
1170 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-19565-4>
1171
- 1172 National Academy of Sciences. (2009). Urban stormwater management in the United States.
1173 Washington, D.C.: National Academies Press.
1174
- 1175 NatureServe. (2023). Biodiversity in Focus: United States Edition (Biodiversity in Focus) (p. 28).
1176 Arlington, VA. Retrieved from <https://www.natureserve.org/bif>
1177
- 1178 Nijssen, M. E., WallisDeVries, M. F., & Siepel, H. (2017). Pathways for the effects of increased
1179 nitrogen deposition on fauna. *Biological Conservation*, 212, 423–431.
1180 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2017.02.022>
1181
- 1182 Noemí Mazía, C., Chaneton, E. J., & Kitzberger, T. (2006). Small-scale habitat use and
1183 assemblage structure of ground-dwelling beetles in a Patagonian shrub steppe. *Journal of Arid*
1184 *Environments*, 67(2), 177–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2006.02.006>
1185
- 1186 Odum, H. T. (1988). Self-Organization, Transformity, and Information. *Science*, 242(4882),
1187 1132–1139. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.242.4882.1132>
1188
- 1189 Oliver, T. H., Marshall, H. H., Morecroft, M. D., Brereton, T., Prudhomme, C., & Huntingford, C.
1190 (2015). Interacting effects of climate change and habitat fragmentation on drought-sensitive
1191 butterflies. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(10), 941–945. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2746>
1192
- 1193 Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., et al.
1194 (2021). The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews.
1195 *BMJ*, n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
1196
- 1197 Pavoine, S., & Bonsall, M. B. (2011). Measuring biodiversity to explain community assembly: a
1198 unified approach. *Biological Reviews*, 86(4), 792–812. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2010.00171.x>
1199

1200
1201 Payne, E. G. I., Pham, T., Deletic, A., Hatt, B. E., Cook, P. L. M., & Fletcher, T. D. (2018). Which
1202 species? A decision-support tool to guide plant selection in stormwater biofilters. *Advances in*
1203 *Water Resources*, 113, 86–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2017.12.022>
1204
1205 Pennsylvania Butterfly Species Occurrence Data Set. (2023, April 19). Global Biodiversity
1206 Information Facility. Retrieved from GBIF.org
1207
1208 Philadelphia Water Department. (2020). Philadelphia Stormwater Management Guidance
1209 Manual, Version 3.2. Appendix I - Table I-1_20150608. Retrieved from
1210 https://www.pwdplanreview.org/upload/pdf/Appendix_I_-_Table_I-1_20150608.pdf
1211
1212 Pille, L., & Säumel, I. (2021). The water-sensitive city meets biodiversity: habitat services of rain
1213 water management measures in highly urbanized landscapes. *Ecology and Society*, 26(2), art23.
1214 <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-12386-260223>
1215
1216 Pitt, R., A. Maestre, & J. Clary. (2018). The National Stormwater Quality Database (NSQD),
1217 Version 4.02. Retrieved from
1218 [https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5f8dbde10268ab224c895ad7/t/5fbd4f842192d61a1f85](https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5f8dbde10268ab224c895ad7/t/5fbd4f842192d61a1f85f71a/1606242187964/NSQD_ver_4_brief_Feb_18_2018.pdf)
1219 [f71a/1606242187964/NSQD_ver_4_brief_Feb_18_2018.pdf](https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5f8dbde10268ab224c895ad7/t/5fbd4f842192d61a1f85f71a/1606242187964/NSQD_ver_4_brief_Feb_18_2018.pdf)
1220
1221 Pöyry, J., Carvalheiro, L. G., Heikkinen, R. K., Kühn, I., Kuussaari, M., Schweiger, O., et al. (2017).
1222 The effects of soil eutrophication propagate to higher trophic levels: Effects of soil
1223 eutrophication on herbivores. *Global Ecology and Biogeography*, 26(1), 18–30.
1224 <https://doi.org/10.1111/geb.12521>
1225
1226 Prince George’s County, Maryland. (2007). Bioretention Manual. Retrieved from
1227 <https://portal.ct.gov/-/media/deep/p2/raingardens/bioretentionmanual2009versionpdf.pdf>
1228
1229 Prince George’s County, Coffman, L. S., Green, R., Engineering Technologies Associates, Inc.,
1230 Clar, M., Engineering Technologies Associates, Inc., et al. (1994). Development of Bioretention
1231 Practices for Stormwater Management. *Journal of Water Management Modeling*.
1232 <https://doi.org/10.14796/JWMM.R176-02>
1233
1234 Prince George’s County, Maryland. (2000). Low-Impact Development Design Strategies (Report
1235 No. EPA 841-B-00-003).
1236
1237 Prudencio, L., & Null, S. E. (2018). Stormwater management and ecosystem services: a review.
1238 *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(3), 033002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaa81a>
1239
1240 Raven, P. H., & Wagner, D. L. (2021). Agricultural intensification and climate change are rapidly
1241 decreasing insect biodiversity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(2),
1242 e2002548117. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2002548117>
1243

- 1244 Robinson, G. S., Ackery, P. R., Kitching, I., Beccaloni, G. W., & Hernández, L. M. (2023). HOSTS - a
1245 Database of the World's Lepidopteran Hostplants [CSV,PDF]. [object Object].
1246 <https://doi.org/10.5519/HAVT50XW>
1247
- 1248 Roy-Poirier, A., Champagne, P., & Fillion, Y. (2010). Review of Bioretention System Research and
1249 Design: Past, Present, and Future. *Journal of Environmental Engineering*, 136(9), 878–889.
1250 [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EE.1943-7870.0000227](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EE.1943-7870.0000227)
1251
- 1252 Sauve, A. M. C., Thébault, E., Pocock, M. J. O., & Fontaine, C. (2015). How plants connect
1253 pollination and herbivory networks and their contribution to community stability. *Ecology*, 15-
1254 0132.1. <https://doi.org/10.1890/15-0132.1>
1255
- 1256 Schueler, T. R., Fraley-McNeal, L., & Capiella, K. (2009). Is Impervious Cover Still Important?
1257 Review of Recent Research. *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering*, 14(4), 309–315.
1258 [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1084-0699\(2009\)14:4\(309\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1084-0699(2009)14:4(309))
1259
- 1260 Sekercioglu, C. H., Daily, G. C., & Ehrlich, P. R. (2004). Ecosystem consequences of bird declines.
1261 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 101(52), 18042–18047.
1262 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0408049101>
1263
- 1264 Settele, J., Kudrna, O., Harpke, A., Kühn, I., van Swaay, C., Verovnik, R., et al. (2008). Climatic
1265 Risk Atlas of European Butterflies. *BioRisk*, 1, 1–712. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biorisk.1>
1266
- 1267 Shaw, D., & Schmidt, R. (2003). Plants for stormwater design: Species Selection for the Upper
1268 Midwest. Minnesota Pollution Control Agency.
1269
- 1270 Shetty, N. H., Mailloux, B. J., McGillis, W. R., & Culligan, P. J. (2020). Observations of the
1271 seasonal buildup and washout of salts in urban bioswale soil. *Science of The Total Environment*,
1272 722, 137834. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137834>
1273
- 1274 Stevens, C. J., David, T. I., & Storkey, J. (2018). Atmospheric nitrogen deposition in terrestrial
1275 ecosystems: Its impact on plant communities and consequences across trophic levels.
1276 *Functional Ecology*, 32(7), 1757–1769. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.13063>
1277
- 1278 Stevens, V. M., Turlure, C., & Baguette, M. (2010). A meta-analysis of dispersal in butterflies.
1279 *Biological Reviews*, no-no. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-185X.2009.00119.x>
1280
- 1281 Tallamy, D. W., & Shriver, W. G. (2021). Are declines in insects and insectivorous birds related?
1282 *Ornithological Applications*, 123(1), duaa059. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ornithapp/duaa059>
1283
- 1284 Townsend, C. R., Begon, M., & Harper, J. L. (2008). *Essentials of ecology* (3rd ed). Malden:
1285 Blackwell Publishing.
1286
- 1287 UK Butterfly Monitoring Scheme. (2021). Retrieved from <https://ukbms.org/>

1288
1289 University of Vermont Spatial Analysis Laboratory. (2016). High-Resolution Land Cover,
1290 Commonwealth of Pennsylvania, Chesapeake Bay Watershed and Delaware River Basin, 2013.
1291 Retrieved from <https://www.pasda.psu.edu/uci/DataSummary.aspx?dataset=3193>
1292
1293 U.S. Army Corps of Engineers. (2020). National Wetland Plant List. (Version 3.5) Retrieved from
1294 <http://wetland-plants.usace.army.mil/>
1295
1296 U.S. Department of Agriculture. (2022). The Plants Database. Greensboro, NC USA. Retrieved
1297 from plants.usda.gov
1298
1299 Van Deynze, B., Swinton, S. M., Hennessy, D. A., Haddad, N. M., & Ries, L. (2024). Insecticides,
1300 more than herbicides, land use, and climate, are associated with declines in butterfly species
1301 richness and abundance in the American Midwest. *PLOS ONE*, 19(6), e0304319.
1302 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0304319>
1303
1304 Veerkamp, C. J., Schipper, A. M., Hedlund, K., Lazarova, T., Nordin, A., & Hanson, H. I. (2021). A
1305 review of studies assessing ecosystem services provided by urban green and blue
1306 infrastructure. *Ecosystem Services*, 52, 101367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101367>
1307
1308 Vitousek, P. M., Aber, J. D., Howarth, R. W., Likens, G. E., Matson, P. A., Schindler, D. W., et al.
1309 (1997). Human Alteration of the Global Nitrogen Cycle: Sources and Consequences. *Ecological*
1310 *Applications*, 7(3), 737–750. [https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(1997)007[0737:HAOTGN]2.0.CO;2)
1311 [0761\(1997\)007\[0737:HAOTGN\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1890/1051-0761(1997)007[0737:HAOTGN]2.0.CO;2)
1312
1313 Wagner, D. L., Fox, R., Salcido, D. M., & Dyer, L. A. (2021). A window to the world of global
1314 insect declines: Moth biodiversity trends are complex and heterogeneous. *Proceedings of the*
1315 *National Academy of Sciences*, 118(2), e2002549117.
1316 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2002549117>
1317
1318 Wagner, D. L., Grames, E. M., Forister, M. L., Berenbaum, M. R., & Stopak, D. (2021). Insect
1319 decline in the Anthropocene: Death by a thousand cuts. *Proceedings of the National Academy*
1320 *of Sciences*, 118(2), e2023989118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2023989118>
1321
1322 WallisDeVries, M. F. (2014). Linking species assemblages to environmental change: Moving
1323 beyond the specialist-generalist dichotomy. *Basic and Applied Ecology*, 15(4), 279–287.
1324 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.baae.2014.05.001>
1325
1326 WallisDeVries, M. F., & van Swaay, C. A. M. (2017). A nitrogen index to track changes in
1327 butterfly species assemblages under nitrogen deposition. *Biological Conservation*, 212, 448–
1328 453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2016.11.029>
1329

- 1330 Wallisdevries, M. F., Van Swaay, C. A. M., & Plate, C. L. (2012). Changes in nectar supply: A
1331 possible cause of widespread butterfly decline. *Current Zoology*, 58(3), 384–391.
1332 <https://doi.org/10.1093/czoolo/58.3.384>
1333
- 1334 Warren, M. S., Maes, D., van Swaay, C. A. M., Goffart, P., Van Dyck, H., Bourn, N. A. D., et al.
1335 (2021). The decline of butterflies in Europe: Problems, significance, and possible solutions.
1336 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 118(2), e2002551117.
1337 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2002551117>
1338
- 1339 Wepprich, T., Adrion, J. R., Ries, L., Wiedmann, J., & Haddad, N. M. (2019). Butterfly abundance
1340 declines over 20 years of systematic monitoring in Ohio, USA. *PLOS ONE*, 14(7), e0216270.
1341 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0216270>
1342
- 1343 Wooster, E. I. F., Fleck, R., Torpy, F., Ramp, D., & Irga, P. J. (2022). Urban green roofs promote
1344 metropolitan biodiversity: A comparative case study. *Building and Environment*, 207, 108458.
1345 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.108458>
1346
- 1347 Yang, Y.-Y., & Toor, G. S. (2016). δ 15 N and δ 18 O Reveal the Sources of Nitrate-Nitrogen in
1348 Urban Residential Stormwater Runoff. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 50(6), 2881–2889.
1349 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b05353>
1350
- 1351 Yoe, C. E., & Orth, K. D. (1996). Planning Manual (No. IWR Report 96-R-21). U.S. Army Corps of
1352 Engineers, Water Resources Support Center, Institute for Water Resources. Retrieved from
1353 <https://www.iwr.usace.army.mil/Portals/70/docs/iwrreports/96r21.pdf>
1354
- 1355 Yoon, S., & Read, Q. (2016). Consequences of exotic host use: Impacts on *Lepidoptera* and a test
1356 of the ecological trap hypothesis. *Oecologia*, 181(4), 985–996. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-016-3560-2)
1357 [016-3560-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-016-3560-2)
1358
- 1359 Zare, F., Jakeman, A. J., Elsayah, S., & Guillaume, J. H. A. (2024). Bridging practice and science in
1360 socio-environmental systems research and modelling: A design science approach. *Ecological*
1361 *Modelling*, 492, 110719. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2024.110719>